

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

THIRTY-SEVENTH ANNUAL REPORT • 1993

**COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
THIRTY-SEVENTH ANNUAL REPORT 1993**

*1400 16th Street, N.W., Suite 510
Washington, D.C. 20036*

The scholar at his book-wheel is a reproduction of an engraving in Agostino Ramelli's *Le diverse et artificiose machine...* Paris, 1588. It first appeared in the Council's third annual report, with the following explanation: "the picture symbolizes the interest of the Council on Library Resources in both the content of books and the mechanics of library service." The engraving has appeared in each annual report since that time.

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-
2. Elected at the November 1992 Directors' meeting.
 3. Until November 1992.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The following foundations were among the supporters of Council activities during 1992/1993. All deserve the thanks of the library community.

The J. Paul Getty Trust

The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation

The W. K. Kellogg Foundation

The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation

CHAIRMAN'S MESSAGE

This past year has been a challenging one for libraries. The increasing demand for services creates overloaded staff. The increasing costs for materials strain decreasing budgets. An increasing number of technological methods of managing information calls into question the role of the library as the primary information provider within the community it serves. The increasing array of formats in which information can appear complicates the means by which libraries gather information and make it available.

At the national level, there is attention to the development of an "information highway" and to "digital" libraries, while at local levels, libraries are reducing hours, cutting staff and services, and, in some cases, closing doors. While knowledge workers are heralded as necessary to the future in this increasingly information-intensive age, our library schools continue to be dismantled.

The Council's broad mandate, "to address the problems of libraries," presents us with ample challenges. In this current, complex environment, we must find a way to make a difference; we are limited only by our financial resources. The Board of Directors has worked closely with our president during the past year to sharpen our focus and to evaluate strategies to assure the continued contribution of the Council to libraries and to the broader society they serve.

Maximilian W. Kemper

PRESIDENT'S MESSAGE

As our Chairman has observed, there are many challenges facing both the Council and the library community it serves. A changing environment is causing all of us to rethink our roles, structures, and focus. To help us with this task, the Council has been holding meetings of individuals associated with research libraries and urban public libraries, along with library educators. The resulting discussions and our assessment of them confirm the need for vision, leadership, and organizational planning to help the library and information services profession play a more proactive role in the information age.

The task before the Council, and the library community in general, is to demonstrate that libraries are crucial to the survival of a democratic society. This is not a simple task. Most sources of funding often do not see the direct connection between their own agenda and the role of libraries. Those who do understand are already stretched thin by more requests than they can fulfill.

At the same time, new technology appears to offer ready access to vast amounts of information, but there are serious barriers that must be overcome if the "digital libraries" now spoken of so often are truly to serve society and not just a technically elite few. Research is needed to address the significant array of problems that create barriers to ready access to the information in our nation's libraries. Such barriers can be technical, economic, organizational, or sociopolitical.

The Council's programs are dedicated to assuring that these barriers are understood and minimized. This year's annual report contains more than details of our current programs, however. It also contains a special insert concerning the history of the Council and its contributions to the library community and society in general. This information, we believe, demonstrates the major influence one organization can have on our nation's information infrastructure, despite relatively limited funding support.

The Council was created to address the problems of libraries and is now committed to the most significant library problem of all—ensuring that library resources are embraced as part of the solution for people who seek to solve their own problems and those of their communities and institutions. In the coming year, the Council must demonstrate clearly its relevance as a means to solve problems, just as libraries must.

W. David Pennington

PROGRAM REVIEW

OVERVIEW

When the Council on Library Resources was created in 1956, its purpose was stated broadly: “to aid in the solution of library problems.” Indicative of the influence that funding sources can have on the Council or any other organization, the general objective expressed in the charter was further specified by the Ford Foundation initiating grant to be “for the purpose of aiding in the solution of the problems of libraries generally, and of research libraries in particular.” Other modifications of the purpose resulting from the initiating grant related to the conduct of research and development, and added to the Council’s role “making grants to other institutions and persons for such purposes; and providing leadership in, and wherever appropriate, coordination of efforts (1) to develop the resources and services of libraries and (2) to improve relations between American and foreign libraries and archives.”¹

As the Council’s chairman stated in his message in last year’s annual report, an analysis of the complex environment in which we operate today indicates that today’s “library problems,” such as shrinking budgets and rising costs, are a subset of larger societal problems. The institutions that libraries serve (e.g., universities, communities, schools, government agencies, and corporations) continue to face economic and sociopolitical challenges of an unprecedented nature. Foundations that traditionally have funded library programs and research have turned to broader societal issues of poverty, health care, urban decay, racial discrimination, failing educational systems, and deteriorating infrastructure, as well as international challenges.

The Council’s assessment of the environment in which it and the libraries it serves must operate includes:

- **A switch to a service-based society**

Organizations are focusing on customer service even though they may still manufacture goods—often in other countries. Other institutions, including universities and other not-for-profit organizations, are beginning to view themselves in this service-based environment from a business viewpoint.

¹ Council on Library Resources, Inc., *FIRST ANNUAL REPORT* (Washington, D.C., 1957), 5.

- **An increased emphasis on “accountability”**

Institutions are being challenged to measure their performance in explicit ways. Institutions that were previously supported routinely are being asked to demonstrate their worth.

- **The changing demographic makeup of the United States**

The shift toward increased cultural diversity has major implications for the work force in the information service arena as well as the user base it will serve.

- **Increasing globalization of institutions**

Countries, industries, and key social institutions are no longer operating in isolation. East and West are meeting in the marketplace as well as in political forums.

- **A troubled economy, both in the United States and worldwide**

Some of our nation’s most vital institutions are having to rethink their levels of spending. At the same time, global economics is playing an increasingly important role as we see the fragmentation of Eastern Europe, the unification of Western Europe, and the continuing emergence of the Pacific Rim as a major economic force.

The trends for the Council’s traditional academic audience include a decline in the college-age population, an impending shortage of Ph.D.-trained faculty, curriculum changes, greater emphasis on and new approaches to teaching, cost control and program redesign due to limited resources, more focus and selectivity in academic programs, and new ways of publishing and evaluating scholarly work. This last trend is the focus of a report from the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, *University Libraries and Scholarly Communication*,² which contains a wealth of information on the state of research libraries today and the electronic possibilities of tomorrow.

² Anthony M. Cummings, et al., *UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES AND SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION: A STUDY PREPARED FOR THE ANDREW W. MELLON FOUNDATION* (Washington, D.C.: The Association of Research Libraries for The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, November 1992).

These trends and the need for libraries to be able to respond to them in new ways were underscored during the year as the Council held focus group sessions for research librarians and urban public librarians. The session participants identified the role of the library, financing and accountability, technology, and adaptation to change as major areas of concern. Each of these topics can be addressed by one of the Council's program areas: adaptation to change is a human resource need, financing and accountability are included in economics, infrastructure addresses the role of the library, and technology is an important component of our access and processing area.

For the Council on Library Resources to address its original purpose, we must continually respond to this changing environment. We must relate the activities of libraries and librarians to the urgent problems of contemporary society, not as another problem, but rather as institutions and individuals capable of providing solutions to broader societal issues. For us, and for many foundations, an implicit goal is to develop self-sufficiency among the communities, groups, and individuals we seek to help. Self-sufficiency in this context means the capability to address long-term problems on one's own without continued intervention.

The overall goals of the Council are to help libraries embrace a forward-looking mission and vision and to help foundations see a close relationship between their objectives and the objectives of the libraries of the future. The Council's four general program areas—human resources, economics, infrastructure, and access and processing—not only have allowed us to address these goals, but also have provided the framework in which previously committed projects have been classified and new projects have been initiated. These programs have been defined broadly enough to provide flexibility, but narrowly enough to focus attention on specific needs in the emerging information service arena.

The report that follows describes both completed and initiated projects in the Council's program areas, and provides a picture of the Council's current activities. Reports on research funded in previous years are also included in this overview. Full citations to the works referenced appear in the bibliography beginning on page 30; current projects are listed in the section beginning on page 36, Grants and Contracts Active in Fiscal 1993.

HUMAN RESOURCES

Throughout its history, the Council has supported efforts to improve the skills of the individuals who direct and staff libraries and information service systems. The current human resources program is intended to develop leaders on a continuing basis who can build and manage the information support systems needed by society and to assist current leaders in developing the skills needed to transform their institutions in response to changing societal needs. This program area emphasizes leadership and management development, recruitment, education, and research.

LEADERSHIP AND MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT

Academic Library Management Intern Program

Two interns participated in this long-standing Council program in 1992-93, bringing to fifty-five the total number of librarians who have honed their management skills by spending an academic year with the director and senior staff of a large and well-managed library. Heather Gordon served her internship with Jerry D. Campbell, University Librarian at Duke University. Judy McQueen interned with Richard De Gennaro, Roy E. Larsen Librarian at Harvard College.

Although the intern program has been very successful since its inception in 1974, as witnessed by the fact that a large percentage of former interns hold directorships or senior administrative positions in major academic libraries, the Council has decided to suspend it indefinitely after the 1992-93 academic year. Evaluation has suggested that there may not be the same need for this kind of program as there was twenty years ago, and that there may be alternative ways of preparing future administrators that would allow greater numbers of people to participate for a similar investment of financial resources.

ACRL/CLS College Library Director Mentor Program

In June 1992, the Council awarded a grant to Eckerd College to cover initial costs, for a two-year period, of a program designed to enhance the leadership capabilities of newly appointed college library directors, many of whom have never served in positions that directly prepare them for leadership in a college library. The program was developed

by the Leadership Committee, College Libraries Section, of the Association of College and Research Libraries and was coordinated by Larry Hardesty of Eckerd College.

New directors participating in the program are matched with experienced college library directors, who act as their mentors or peer consultants. Nominations for participation in the program come from new directors themselves or from academic deans who have recently hired new directors. CLR funds support campus visits between each pair of individuals, telephone communication, and a three-day seminar at the end of each year for the new directors.

Fourteen first-year directors participated in the program during the 1992-93 academic year. In general, the relationships were very productive, helping to counter the isolation from peers that many new directors feel, and contributing a new perspective to the experienced library directors. Support for this program from academic deans has been positive as well. The first year ended successfully with a three-day seminar held at Loyola University in New Orleans prior to the annual American Library Association meeting in June.

LIBRARY AND INFORMATION STUDIES CURRICULA

Education for Diversity

The Council made a grant this year to the Graduate School of Library and Information Studies at Queens College/CUNY to conduct a series of four seminars/workshops centered around multiculturalism and diversity in the work place. Although the school has a major commitment to diversity—as represented by the composition of its student body, availability of fellowships, and courses offered—faculty feel that they do not know enough about issues related to multiculturalism. The intent of the workshops is to draw on resources of the metropolitan New York community to identify primary areas of concern relating to the topic. This activity will contribute to new strategies for redesigning the curriculum in order to provide improved services to a multicultural audience. Two seminars were conducted during the 1992-93 academic year; the remaining two are scheduled for the fall of 1993.

Knowledge and Skills for Health Information Professionals

Changes in the health information environment have presaged significant changes in the knowledge and skills

expected of health information professionals in the future. However, there is little research on which to base judgments about what general areas of expertise are likely to be required. Fred Roper, Dean of the College of Library and Information Science at the University of South Carolina, and Chair of the Medical Library Association (MLA) Knowledge and Skills Task Force, was principal investigator of a 1990 grant intended to assess the present level of specific knowledge and skills among health science librarians and their perceptions about requirements for the future. The report of the survey was completed in the fall of 1992.

The report proved influential. An MLA educational policy statement, *Platform for Change*, adopted by its Board of Directors in December 1991, is a major by-product of the survey. Its implementation is considered an MLA priority. The *Platform* describes the needs for lifelong, interdisciplinary learning for the field, anticipates that the amount of health care information will continue to grow exponentially, and predicts that health care will be one of the nation's most critical information issues. Using the results of the survey, the Knowledge and Skills Task Force of MLA developed a comprehensive plan for education for health information specialists throughout an individual's career, including a strong continuing education role by the Medical Library Association and the National Library of Medicine (NLM). NLM is currently using the results of the research in a planning panel it has established to consider education and training.

FUTURE OF EDUCATION FOR LIBRARIANSHIP

The Council contracted with the Palmer School of Library and Information Science, Long Island University, to survey the relevant literature and prepare an annotated bibliography and report synthesizing emerging trends and concepts in library and information science education. The results will be used to facilitate CLR planning for projects and programs in our human resources area.

STRATEGIC VISIONS

The Council's 1992 annual report described the formation and initial meetings of the Strategic Visions Discussion Group, formed by a group of librarians interested in the role of the librarian and the library of the future. A draft vision statement and a discussion draft of the values and qualities

of librarianship that will be desirable in the next century were generated during the first year.

Susan Martin described the group's formation in the proceedings of the 1992 President's Program of the Association for Library Collections and Technical Services. With its September 1992 issue, the *Journal of Academic Librarianship* established a regular "Visions" column to address the coming changes for libraries and the profession itself. In the first column, Don Bosseau and Susan Martin provided some background on the strategic visions group. The Palmer School of Library and Information Science, Long Island University, used Strategic Visions documents and members of the Strategic Visions Group to facilitate the planning process as part of its reaccreditation effort.

This year, discussions continued at the national and local levels and were assisted by the operations of an open listserv connection for the Strategic Visions Group. The electronic mail facility, established at San Diego State University, generated over 1,000 messages among its 348 subscribers in the first year of operation.

RESEARCH REPORTS

Recruitment, Job Classification, and Promotion in Libraries

Recruiting and retaining qualified students interested in library and information science is of paramount importance to the profession. Over the years, a relatively high percentage (1.7 percent) of graduates of Earlham College, a four-year liberal arts college in Richmond, Indiana, have become librarians, a percentage about six times the national average for undergraduates. Evan Farber conducted a survey of the Earlham graduates who became librarians to determine why they made their decisions to pursue training for the profession. The most influential factors were "experience using the library at Earlham" and "relationship with a professional librarian at Earlham." It is useful to be reminded of the connection between Earlham's high recruitment into the profession and the fact that its library staff have been leaders in developing bibliographic instruction for students and in promoting integration of the library into the undergraduate curriculum.

Ellen Altman and Patricia Promis investigated the extent to which equal opportunity and affirmative action guidelines have affected recruitment and promotion for the groups

covered by those regulations to management positions in academic libraries. The study concluded that the gender and ethnicity of the candidates finally selected for management positions strongly resembled those of their predecessors. The study found that culturally diverse candidates received equal opportunity: they were hired in proportion to their representation in the applicant pool. There is no statistical evidence, however, that they received affirmative action.

Anne Woodsworth, Theresa Maylone, and Myron Sywak examined whether the converging functions of computing centers and libraries in research universities affected job classification and compensation systems. The results of the study indicated that, when job descriptions of each group are translated into uniform terms, the correlations between library and computing jobs are strong enough to merit considering a single "information job" family in classification systems at organizations that are integrating information technologies. By using this technique, human resource planners can develop a set of factors for job analysis that will articulate the overall information vision and values of each institution, thereby stimulating organizational change.

Library and Information Science Faculty

Two teams of investigators surveyed faculty who teach at schools of library and information science.

Mary Biggs and Victor Biggs reported on a 1988-89 study of full-time faculty at accredited library schools that replicated in methodology an American Council of Learned Societies' (ACLS) 1985 survey of liberal arts faculty in seven social sciences and humanities disciplines. The survey assembled comparison data on the faculties' collegial research relationships, publishing and other scholarly and professional activity, attitudes toward scholarly publishing, scholarly and professional reading, use of libraries, computer use and skills, and overall job satisfaction. The hypothesis was that library school faculty, as members of a "practicing" profession, would possess more sophisticated library-use skills but would be less likely than the ACLS respondents to publish productively or be active professionally as speakers, editors, and referees, and that they would express more dissatisfaction with their professional literature and their jobs. This hypothesis was not supported. As a group, library school faculty reported equal or greater job satisfaction, collegial research relationships, volume of publication and participa-

tion in publication-related activities, satisfaction with their professional literature, and computer literacy than their ACLS counterparts. The ACLS and Biggs studies are not directly comparable because of the three years that separated them and different methods of selecting subjects. However, the Biggs study reveals general productivity and job satisfaction among library school faculty.

Fay Zipkowitz and Elizabeth Futas reported on a 1989-90 survey of library and information science faculty at U.S. and Canadian institutions to determine the projected future need for replacement faculty. The impetus for the study came from several factors: that students entering the library field tend to be older than students in other disciplines; that library science faculty may have shorter academic careers than other teaching faculty because typically they practice librarianship before teaching it; that there is competition for individuals with Ph.D.s within other areas of the profession; and, finally, that because of shrinking financial resources, academic faculty generally have not been hired to replace senior faculty.

The survey found that the average full-time library science faculty member would be 55 years old in 1993. Sixty percent of faculty indicated, in response to a survey question, that they expected to leave teaching before retiring. Predictive models were used by the researchers to conclude that there will be a serious depletion of faculty in library schools before the year 2001 and that immediate plans should be made to recruit, educate, and retain qualified new faculty.

ECONOMICS

In order to assure that the resources invested in libraries and related information services are allocated effectively to maximize the benefits to society in areas of pressing social need, the Council has been addressing projects that focus attention on the costs and benefits of specific library services. The results from such projects should lead to a more systematic decision-making process regarding allocation of funding and cost sharing. An important component in the economics program is the emphasis on a total quality management or continuous improvement thrust within the library community.

The economics studies completed or initiated this year tended to focus on microeconomic issues, addressing such topics as serial pricing, journal use, interlibrary loan, and public library financing. In addition, the Council continued to encourage the application to library services of continuous quality techniques, a practice borrowed from the business community. Support and encouragement for the development of functional tools for libraries to use to determine their own costs and benefits was also included in this year's economics program. The William and Flora Hewlett Foundation has provided most of the resources for Council activities in the program area of economics.

Serial Pricing

Co-investigators George A. Chressanthis, Associate Professor of Economics, and June D. Chressanthis, Assistant Professor and Serials Cataloger, Mississippi State University, prepared several papers and presentations related to an econometric analysis of the determinants of library subscription prices of the top-ranked economics journals. The research data also generated information on the relationship between manuscript submission fees and journal quality, the effect of exchange rate risk on library subscriptions, and publisher monopoly power and third-degree price discrimination. The significance of the Chressanthis' research is in their comprehensive data set and solid methodology within a specific discipline. Similar studies could be conducted for other disciplines.

Journal Use

As serial prices continue to rise, decisions to cancel specific titles must take into account the use of individual serial titles by library clientele. Marifran Bustion and John L. Eltinge reported on the relationships among departmental ratings and subscription costs, the academic discipline and departmental ratings, and the academic discipline and subscription costs. While higher-rated periodicals had higher mean and median prices, the investigators concluded that the relationship between cost and relative price increases is complex. Along with John Harer, they also examined the merits of direct observation of periodical usage. Maiken Naylor compared two methodologies for counting current periodical use and identified the limitations of each method.

Major journal use studies are currently being conducted by Columbia University; the State University of New York campuses at Albany, Binghamton, Buffalo, and Stony Brook; and the Triangle Research Libraries Network as part of their strategic planning grant activities (see description beginning on page 21). As part of the larger project, the Research Foundation of the State University of New York was funded to study the non-participation factor of a journal use survey at the Science and Engineering Library at SUNY-Buffalo. Results from all projects are expected by late fall 1993.

Interlibrary Loan Costs

The Council provided partial support for a project to examine the costs to research libraries of interlibrary loan (ILL) services. Data collection was completed for seventy-six libraries on the typical costs of ILL transactions, based on a survey instrument developed by the Research Libraries Group (RLG) and distributed by the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) to collect cost information for 1991 interlibrary loan borrowing and lending operations. The report was prepared by Marilyn M. Roche, Research Libraries Group. The data show that a research library spends an average of \$18.62 to borrow a document/article or to purchase a photocopy of the item for a patron, and \$10.93 to lend a document to another library. Staff costs represent about 77 percent of the cost for borrowing or lending. The results of the study should help libraries better assess the economics of their own borrowing and lending practices, evaluate alternative methods of providing these services, and analyze the impact of local serials cancellations.

The Council is also providing support for the travel, communication, and office expenses of the ARL Visiting Program Officer, Mary Jackson, to address an ARL initiative to improve interlibrary loan and document delivery services. The results of the ARL/RLG interlibrary loan study point to a need for an ideal interlibrary loan system as proposed in a white paper prepared by Ms. Jackson and Shirley Baker (Dean of University Libraries, Washington University) for the ARL Committee on Access to Information Resources. During her tenure with ARL, Ms. Jackson will follow up on the recommendations in the white paper and will work with libraries and ILL/document delivery system designers to move toward a more comprehensive and integrated system for interlibrary loan and document delivery.

Public Library Financing

A seminar examining the results of a study on public library financing conducted for the U.S. Department of Education, Office of Library Programs, was supported by a 1992 CLR grant to the Urban Libraries Council. Two publications resulted: *Keeping the Book* summarizes the research and study on exemplary public library financial practices supported by a Title II-B grant and provided some of the background material for the seminar, while *Balancing the Book* is based on the papers and discussions of the seminar itself.

Costs and Beneficial Impacts of Library Operations

Libraries today must make planning allocations concerning both new and old modes of access to information. Included in the decision process are factors such as timeliness, thoroughness, convenience, accuracy, and precision. The decisions themselves require knowledge of the expected impact and the expected costs of each course of action. The Council funded a proposal from Rutgers University to develop useful tools to measure the costs, classify the benefits, and measure the benefits of diverse library functions. The project's objectives are to adapt functional cost analysis to all types of library functions and services, to develop a taxonomy to classify library beneficial impacts, and to develop a metrology (measurement science) for measuring benefits as described by the taxonomy. The project investigators will develop techniques and a methodology that will be assembled into a manual, which will subsequently enable other libraries to use the measurements

that are defined from the project or to define their own, as appropriate.

Total Quality Management (TQM)

In an article in the *Journal of Library Administration*, Council president W. David Penniman called for the development of a Malcolm Baldrige award for the library community. He argued that an award would encourage the development of total quality management practices in libraries.

The Council cosponsored with the Special Libraries Association (SLA) a series of workshops on "The Quality Imperative." A total of 226 participants attended the workshops, which were offered in six locations. Course evaluations rated the workshop overall as "very good to excellent." The workshop was also used as part of a three-day conference on total quality held in Los Angeles in early 1993. It was used also as the basis to develop a course on benchmarking, a topic the Council sees as a critical component in the effective implementation of TQM. Total quality management principles have taken hold in the academic community as well, and several universities have begun quality improvement programs that involve the library.

INFRASTRUCTURE

The Council's infrastructure program area is intended to establish continuing communication and cooperation among the various information systems and services that support our libraries and to assure that economic, sociopolitical, technical, and legal changes do not inhibit library functions or access to information by individuals and groups. The Council is interested in finding those key pressure points where we can help strengthen the information infrastructure.

Infrastructure is an umbrella term for the systems, services, and facilities that are drawn upon to help libraries and other information services operate more efficiently and effectively. Under this umbrella we include communication networks, bibliographic utilities, software and hardware vendor communities, and publishers. In addition, we consider current physical structures (i.e., buildings) essential to the delivery of information and an important component of infrastructure. This program area deals with the people, policies, and politics of cooperation and collaboration.

NATIONAL ENGINEERING INFORMATION INITIATIVE

Background

Last year's annual report described the birth of a national initiative to solve a generally recognized problem with engineering information and data: the extremely complex nature of access to the store of engineering expertise and how this complexity inhibits the nation's ability to compete in the international industrial arena. Improving access to technical information resources at the national level will yield a significant return on investment and, at the same time, improve our competitive stance.

The June 1992 conference cosponsored by the Council on Library Resources and the Engineering Foundation (with supplemental support from the AT&T Foundation and the National Science Foundation) resulted in an integrated action plan to improve access to engineering information in libraries and specialized information services in the United States. The Council's report of the conference proceedings, *Exploration of a National Engineering Information Service*, was published in December 1992.¹

¹ Available for \$50 from Media Services Printing, B10 MVR Hall, Cornell University, Ithaca, NY 14853.

This effort has since become known as the National Engineering Information Initiative (NEII). The Council is functioning as the prime mover to maintain the progress of the NEII toward the realization of a national engineering information network. The NEII work is proceeding in accordance with the original integrated action plan presented in last year's annual report.

The Committee for Establishment of GENESIS (The CEG)

The top-down component of the integrated action plan called for the commissioning of a high-level panel to be known as GENESIS, which will provide the conceptualization, strategic direction, planning, design, administration, sanction, and oversight required to promote the development of a national engineering information network. The Council has coordinated the formation and operation of the CEG, which has succeeded in developing:

- a charter for the GENESIS Group;
- a staffing plan for GENESIS, including organizational elements, functions, an estimate of staff costs, position descriptions, and identification of potential candidates for the defined positions; and
- a definition of potential alternative roles for GENESIS in pursuing the integrated action plan.

Tasks remaining for the CEG include finding a home base for GENESIS, seeking a funding base for GENESIS, and initiating GENESIS operations.

Funding the NEII Integrated Action Plan

The Council is carrying forth an aggressive program to acquire funding for the NEII action plan. Still pending are proposals to:

- fund several specific elements of the overall action plan, the Engineering Information Proficiency Initiative, the GENESIS Group Initiative, and the initiative to encourage self-funded pilot projects;
- fund the entire NEII action plan for the first three years; and
- fund a segment of the overall users study assessing the usage and needs of the users of chemical engineering information and data.

Under development and soon to be submitted are proposals to:

- fund another segment of the user audience made up of engineers and their supporting staff directly involved in the manufacturing process in any or all industries;
- fund a program to experiment with several universities to improve engineering curricula in the area of engineering information management and application; and
- fund a prototype model of the NEII to be developed jointly by the Council and the National Institute for Science and Technology.

In addition to these funding initiatives, the Council is involved with engineering societies, corporations, and government agencies engaged in the development of the national data highway and high-performance computing initiatives.

Corporate Sector Support

The Council intends to approach a variety of major U.S. corporations for financial support in the form of interim funding to maintain the initial momentum for the NEII until longer-term funding materializes. The approach will involve mailing a brochure and cover letter to a large number of corporations that would benefit from a national system.

Computer Discussion Group

With the cooperation of the Coalition for Networked Information (CNI), a list server was established that is available to all interested individuals and groups who wish to exchange information and ideas. To subscribe to this list, send electronic mail to listserv@cni.org with the message: subscribe neii <your name> and you will be added to the discussion group.

NEII Focus Group Sessions

In order to interest and involve a wider audience in NEII activities, focus group sessions will be conducted with engineers in government, universities, and industry. The focus groups will explore with the engineers the types of barriers encountered in performing everyday engineering tasks with an eye to discovering the importance of improving access to both internal and external engineering information and data. A second outcome of the focus groups will be to provide additional direction to our planned research

into the needs of engineers for a national information network, one of the specific initiatives of the NEII action plan.

SETTING LIBRARY POLICIES AND PRIORITIES IN RESEARCH UNIVERSITIES

A special grant program for studying future management and service issues in research institutions and their libraries and for developing strategic plans to deal with those issues was announced in the spring of 1990. The grant program was developed in response to the work of the Council's Research Library Committee, which had been considering issues related to the transformation of the teaching and learning information base by integrated information technologies such as computers, telecommunications, and text storage systems. The committee recognized that it was not clear how libraries and faculties would respond to increasing electronic information and the unbounded, unlimited access called for by these new technologies. It was also unclear to the committee if universities and their libraries would be able to embrace this new digital environment productively or if they would be engulfed by it.

The "Statement from the Research Library Committee" (May 1990) concluded that universities would need to undertake a fundamental rethinking of library and information service objectives and, indeed, to consider a redefinition of the role of the research library. Several policy questions were identified; the Council's 1990 annual report includes those questions and subsequent recommendations by the Research Library Committee.

The grant program encouraged universities to begin to address policy questions through a planning process. It did not prescribe how the process should be organized, or which of the questions should be given priority. The program did recommend the active participation of faculty, administration, and the library staff.

Four grants were awarded, and the projects began in 1991. All are nearing completion and final reports are expected in late 1993, but it should be noted that in all cases the process of planning will be continuing. Grant recipients uniformly report that major benefits from this program have been the establishment of a process for planning, the engagement of university faculty and administration in that process, a

reconceptualization about how the institution can respond to the changing environment, and the development of tools to support data-driven decision making.

Columbia University

Data collection and analysis have been completed for the study and survey of library use and users in three science departments—biology, physics, and electrical engineering. The costs of interlibrary borrowing and document delivery were compared with that of ownership, and results confirm that, if cost is the only consideration, it is less expensive either to purchase articles in lesser-used journals or to request them through interlibrary loan than it is to buy those journals in anticipation of need. However, cost is not the only consideration. Related studies of unbound periodical use show that browsing new periodicals is an important source of information for the library's users. Columbia's project team also found that users of electronic information resources make use of a wider range of information than those who do not use electronic services such as online databases or CD-ROM. Users in the sciences also prefer policies that tend toward the ownership of journals and electronic indexes, but this view could change if electronic browsing and document delivery services were developed to become more than substitutes. Columbia also found that, as with most academic libraries, the effect of inflation on the acquisition of science periodicals has been detrimental to their budget. As part of their project, the Columbia study team also visited libraries at six institutions—AT&T Bell Laboratories, Carnegie Mellon University, Cornell University, IBM (Yorktown), the University of Pennsylvania, and Yale University—to identify different models for information delivery that could be incorporated into Columbia's existing electronic infrastructure.

The documentation and detail of the studies and surveys not only provide a valuable base for future planning by Columbia University Libraries, but also present useful models for replication by institutions that expect to take on similar projects.

Harvard University

For Harvard University, the strategic planning grant coincided with a significant period of change in the Harvard College Library. In addressing the need to respond to

changing technology, economics, scholarship, and teaching within a research institution, Harvard found that a key to success was an initial emphasis on vision and a continuing focus on organizational development. Their vision statement presents a future scenario based not on the current organization, but on the role and function of the Harvard College Library ten years hence. Supplementing the vision is a statement of values that expresses the nature of the organization Harvard wished to create. A Staff and Organizational Development Taskforce was charged with defining the strategy to address organizational change.

The most important goal included in the Harvard College Library strategic plan was the retrospective conversion and addition to HOLLIS, their online catalog, of pre-1976 catalog records. Five million records will be converted to machine-readable form in the next six years in one of the largest projects of its kind, and the records will be added to the OCLC and RLG/RLIN databases. This project also helps to address the critical space problems facing Harvard by ensuring more effective management of the materials transferred to the Harvard Depository.

Harvard also plans to share information about organizational change and revitalization with the larger library community. Invitational symposia are scheduled in late 1993 to address the changing role of the library in learning, teaching, and research, while the process of planning within Harvard College Library continues.

State University of New York University Center Libraries

Building on a strong foundation of interinstitutional collaboration, the SUNY Center libraries have been developing multilevel committee structures for planning and policy setting related to an integrated acquisitions plan for four institutions within the statewide system. The libraries recognized that policies needed to be based on relevant data; they conducted a journal overlap study, a current journal titles use study, an interlibrary loan survey, and a faculty electronic access survey. In addition to gathering the necessary data on which to base current and future decisions, the studies and surveys also helped to increase communication, raise awareness, and enlist the cooperation of the communities served by the four libraries.

The studies demonstrated that an unexpectedly high number of unique journal titles exist in the four collections; a

significant number of journal titles at each campus can be considered low-use titles; an acceptable fill rate for interlibrary loan is possible through the use of the combined collections; and the primary obstacles to electronic information access for faculty lie in a lack of knowledge of what is available, coupled with a need for training.

The goal of the grant, to develop the policies and plans for implementation of an active program of cooperative collection development and resource sharing among the SUNY University Center libraries, has been achieved. Its success will be validated by the continuing cooperative policy development process and the engagement of the libraries' staffs, administrators, and faculties.

TRIANGLE RESEARCH LIBRARIES NETWORK

Duke University, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, and North Carolina State University have also been conducting user surveys and studies to gather data on their collective collection strengths. Included in the data is a statistical profile of faculty, graduate students, and grant funding in each of the science and engineering departments of the three universities. The statistics show a high geographic concentration of science and engineering graduate education.

A large-scale survey of all faculty and a large sample of the graduate students in science and engineering departments of the three research universities was conducted in the spring of 1992. The study was modeled on a similar survey conducted by the librarians at Columbia University. The data complement findings from Columbia and SUNY regarding the use of materials and library services. After careful analysis of the data, the research team is now exploring some key policy questions with focus groups on each campus.

In addition to the original proposal to examine cooperative collection development and access for materials and electronic media for the science community, an unexpected result from the planning process has been the development and drafting of a proposed new model university policy suggesting that faculty retention of copyright for the articles they publish in scholarly journals is a necessary precondition for strengthening existing or developing alternative low-cost mechanisms for the dissemination of research results. The draft policy has been widely disseminated and discussed at meetings of librarians, publishers, and academic faculty.

Standards

The National Information Standards Organization (NISO) completed work during the year on durable hardcover bindings for books. Council-supported work continues to develop additional NISO technical standards for the preservation and conservation of library materials.

Scholarly Communication

The Council partially supported a conference organized by the Getty Art History Information Program and the American Council of Learned Societies in the fall of 1992 to address the implications of electronic information for scholarship in the humanities. Papers by Oleg Grabar, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton University; Carolyn Lougee, Stanford University; Richard Lanham, University of California, Los Angeles; William Y. Arms, Carnegie Mellon University; and Lawrence Dowler, Harvard University, provided the invited group of scholars, administrators, librarians, technologists, and leaders of national institutions and learned societies with information about how current trends in information technology will affect the humanities. A summary of the proceedings includes excerpts from the keynote address by Vartan Gregorian, President, Brown University, along with summaries of the discussion papers, findings from the working groups, and comments and conclusions from the conference organizers. The participants developed recommendations, including the initiation of a national collaborative effort for the humanities, promotion of the creation of a national "digital" library, development of model collaborative projects, support for training, promotion of an understanding of the role that information technology can play in research and teaching, and establishment of descriptive standards for primary materials.

In a similar vein, a one-day seminar in April 1993 was held at the College of William and Mary to explore the topic of scholarly humanities communication in the electronic age. Scholars, librarians, and the public were invited to share information on current projects and to discuss the trends affecting the way people use technology to create, retrieve, and manipulate information. Keynote speakers alternated with case studies and provided an atmosphere of interactive learning during the seminar, which was partially supported by the Council.

Institutional Collaboration

To investigate how librarians can work with computer scientists and university faculty in a collaborative setting demonstrating a virtual library concept, the Council has awarded a grant to Rice University for partial support of a project to develop materials for an undergraduate course on science in early modern Europe within the university's electronic studio project. The project will incorporate an advanced technology, the Virtual Notebook System (VNS), which is a distributed multimedia hypertext system. The electronic studio is analogous to an architect's studio, where a drafting table and storage cabinet serve as a permanent work place and repository for tools, design projects, and personal possessions. Materials collected by librarians, faculty, and students in fully developed electronic studios will include notes, assignments, documents, images, video, and sound. Roles and responsibilities of the librarians, faculty members, and computer scientists, as well as the management and utilization of technologies, will be assessed as part of the project.

Network Advisory Committee

The Council continues to provide modest support to the Network Advisory Committee (NAC). Membership in the Network Advisory Committee is composed of U.S. organizations formally constituted and functioning in the public and private (for-profit or not-for-profit) sectors that are actively engaged in regional or nationwide networking of library and information services, or have a significant impact on the development of nationwide networks providing library and information services.

The December 1992 meeting explored the topic of "Multimedia and Networking." Guest speakers included Dr. Robert Heterick, President of EDUCOM; Howard Besser, Canadian Center for Architecture; William Harless, Time Associates, Ltd.; David Bearman, Archives and Museum Informatics; John Clement, EDUCOM; and Carl Fleischhauer, Library of Congress. Meeting participants saw demonstrations of multimedia for different communities (education, scientific, museum, etc.) at the National Demonstration Laboratory for Interactive Information Technology at the Library of Congress. A panel presentation on the implications of multimedia for the information community concluded the meeting. The proceedings will be published as Library of Congress Network Planning Paper no. 24.

The June 1993 meeting was devoted to an exploration of the educational requirements for information professionals from the perspective of national networking initiatives. Members of ALISE (Association for Library and Information Science Education) participated in the meeting. Speakers from both the Network Advisory Committee and ALISE provided overviews of the roles of networkers and of library and information science programs. Topics included overviews of each organization, updates on current national legislation, issues facing higher education, the changing curriculum, distance learning, and continuing education. The proceedings will also be published as a network planning paper.

Network Planning Paper No. 23, "The Role of State Library Agencies in the Evolving National Information Network," based on the April 1992 NAC meeting, was published and distributed in 1993.

Community Networking

It is expected that within the next few years, electronic communications and multimedia information resources will be delivered to communities and homes across the country. What impact these services will have on libraries and individuals is the subject of an initial evaluation of the Blacksburg Electronic Village Project. The project is a joint effort of the Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, the Town of Blacksburg, and C&T Telephone/Bell Atlantic Company. Over the next three years, high-speed data connections and Internet access will be brought to homes, schools, libraries, and businesses in the community of Blacksburg. The Electronic Village Project is serving as a prototype for bringing interactive library resources to people in the community. The initial evaluation, funded by CLR, will gauge the impact of new electronic information services on libraries and individuals; determine which information services have the greatest value to users by looking at pricing, billing, and other delivery issues; assess the user interface and other technical aspects of the information services; and refine evaluation methods and techniques in order to make improvements before a subsequent full-scale evaluation of the project.

Libraries and Technology

The historical attitudes of librarians toward technological devices and the role of innovations in shaping the development of library processes and services is chronicled in a new

monograph by Klaus Musmann. His survey of the professional literature documents aspects of the link between society and the library. He found that librarians have been remarkably willing to experiment with new technologies and adapt them to library activities.

International Activities

The Council's international activities this year were concentrated on support for the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA). Funded by the Council in 1989 and administered by IFLA, the Robert Vosper IFLA Fellows Program awarded fellowships on a competitive basis to outstanding librarians with an interest in and a commitment to the international aspects of library service. The program was named after Robert Vosper, Honorary Fellow of IFLA, and a former CLR Board member (now Director Emeritus). The purpose of the fellowships was to enable librarians with the potential for leadership and international involvement to develop this potential by working on an activity linked with the development and operation of one of IFLA's Core Programmes.

A total of twelve fellowships were awarded during the four-year program, and topics addressed by the Vosper Fellows covered the broad range of IFLA interests: preservation, bibliographic control, interlending and document supply, library education, and technology. Project reports are being published by the IFLA Core Programmes. The 1989 class members were: Mark Roosa (University of Delaware, USA); Marc Walckiers (Université de Louvain, Brussels, Belgium); and Johanna Wellheiser (Metropolitan Toronto Reference Library, Toronto, Canada). Members of the 1990 class were: Françoise Bourdon (Bibliothèque Nationale, Paris, France) and Jay Lambrecht (University of Illinois at Chicago). The 1991 class included Michele Cloonan (University of California, Los Angeles); Barbara Stefaniak (Institute for Scientific, Technical and Economic Information, Warsaw, Poland); and Titia van der Werf (RABIN, The Hague, Netherlands). The class of 1992 included Georgeta Clinca (Biblioteca Nationala a Romaniei, Bucharest, Romania); Craig Ross Fairley (Metropolitan Toronto Reference Library, Toronto, Ontario, Canada); Elda-Monica Guerrero (Centro de Investigación y Docencia Economicas, Mexico); and Wendy Smith (National Library of Australia, Canberra, Australia).

ACCESS AND PROCESSING

The rapid increase in the amount and availability of information, the variety of means by which that information can now be delivered, and the concomitant and increasing costs for acquiring and processing information challenge the traditional processing and access activities of libraries. The Council on Library Resources has continually sought to improve the methods by which libraries acquire, organize, store, retrieve, reproduce, and make available information for efficient use by the communities they serve. That use may be to answer questions, to solve problems, or for an individual's personal or professional development. The Council's current access and processing program seeks to create ongoing mechanisms that enhance access to information by encouraging improvement in the internal processes performed by our libraries so that the resources invested in libraries are used more efficiently and effectively.

Information Search Process

System developers are continually trying to improve the tools and processes that help library users obtain access to the information they seek. In order to make improvements in the tools, developers and managers need to know how users are getting their information now, the limitations that exist in current systems, and what system features are most useful to individuals.

Martha Andrews conducted a study of the information needs of geology and geography graduate students, research associates, and faculty. Traditional sources such as conversations with colleagues, references at the end of articles, and personal collections are still their main information sources.

The interdisciplinary nature of library users' research interests was investigated by Laura Bartolo and Timothy Smith. They compared the impact of manual and online search methods on the interdisciplinary search task in terms of the relevance of retrieved items, user effort, user satisfaction, user confidence, and future use. The results indicated that online search methods are more effective than manual searches when users are working outside their areas of specialization.

Ann Bishop is exploring how engineers in the aerospace industry utilize electronic communications. Preliminary

results suggest that networks are used widely for both internal and external communications. However, network use is currently limited by its inability to convey the multifaceted information needed by engineers to address complex problems.

Many users get rather poor results when searching CD-ROM databases, reported F.W. Lancaster and his colleagues from the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign Graduate School of Library and Information Science. Searches performed by faculty and graduate students were compared both with searches conducted by an experienced education librarian and with those conducted by a team of experienced searchers. While the library users did find pertinent items, they did not find them all, nor did they find the best.

While Lancaster compared user searches with those of experienced searchers, Gary Marchionini and his research team examined the searching behavior of professional search intermediaries and subject experts. The researchers determined that the domain experts were content-driven and used technical query terms based on their knowledge, while the search experts were problem-driven and used system features to refine their results. System designers will need to take both types of users into account when making improvements to their systems.

Maxine Reneker's dissertation was a study of the information-seeking activities of thirty-one members of the Stanford University academic community. Using a naturalistic approach, Reneker recorded the information needs they experienced, how they went about answering them, the sources of information they used, and their level of satisfaction with the information. The picture that emerged from the study was that the individuals were active information seekers who see their information environment in a positive light. They seek information as a result of a need, and there is a dynamic relationship between the environment, information sources, and the articulation of a need.

Catholic University investigators Ingrid Hsieh-Yee and Tom Marcum have been funded to study how faculty members seek information and how they use an online system. The project objectives include determining how information-seeking patterns are related to discipline, how online systems facilitate faculty information seeking, and how faculty use the online system. Data on faculty members at four

institutions sharing a common online system will be gathered, and results are expected in 1994.

A study of the information-seeking process among a select group of social science and medical faculty researchers in the field of population studies is being conducted by L. Terri Singer, now at the University of South Florida, and Kenneth H. Hill at Johns Hopkins University. This study is comparing researcher and librarian searches of the CD-ROM POPLINE, a database on population and family planning. Results are expected in late 1993.

Bibliographic Control

Begun in 1971, the Library of Congress' Cataloging in Publication (CIP) program provides prepublication cataloging records for the books most likely to be acquired by libraries. Findings from a survey of CIP beneficiaries were prepared by SKP Associates and published in 1993 by the Library of Congress. Libraries of all types were surveyed; librarians, publishers, and MARC tape recipients all agreed that the program continues to be a valuable one. The Council supported this survey of two decades of CIP and had supported a similar study conducted after CIP's first ten years of operation. The Council was also instrumental in the establishment of the CIP program. Results from the 1993 study indicated that the scope and quality of the data are above average, and savings in cataloging costs for libraries are significant. The challenge for the program in the coming year will be to demonstrate its ability to respond to the diversity of CIP users and the demands of a changing publishing environment.

How best to catalog cooperatively continues to challenge the library community. As technologies change and systems improve, cataloging personnel and their managers must adjust to new priorities and workflows. Each decade brings different perspectives on how to share the burden of providing bibliographic descriptions and access to an increasing number of new publications that appear each year in an increasing array of different formats. This year, a Cooperative Cataloging Council was established to develop a strategic plan for cooperative cataloging among the nation's libraries. The effort came out of a joint meeting of representatives from the National Coordinated Cataloging Program and the CONSER Program, who saw the need for a model program that would take the best from existing programs

and set the stage for a more cost-effective, participatory process. A mission statement was prepared, goals were established, and several task forces were formed to address specific issues. CLR provided support for a planning meeting of the group in April 1993, and task forces are continuing their work throughout the summer and fall of 1993.

One of the new forms of publication for which access mechanisms need to be developed is preprints. Katherine Branch reported on a Yale University project to establish an alternative electronic distribution system for mathematics preprints that also included an exploration of how electronic distribution affects use. Key findings included identification of the technical barriers to access and assessment of some sociological issues of scientific communication.

Henry Snyder and Heidi Hutchinson conducted a comparative and analytical study of cataloging rules employed in Europe for an older form of publication, materials printed by use of a hand press. This report was prepared for the working group appointed by the organizers of the Munich 1990 Conference on Retrospective Cataloging and Conversion in Europe.

Françoise Bourdon, a Vosper Fellow, also looked at broader cataloging issues by investigating name authority control at the international level. Her study included an examination of the existing document on name authority files and eight automated files. She identified the problems encountered in exchanging authority data at the international level and recommended action by the appropriate national and international agencies.

The distribution of responsibilities for accessioning and indexing arctic regions information is being investigated by Martha Andrews through a grant to the University of Colorado. Data have been collected to identify overlapping coverage and absence of coverage of the arctic literature in databases of the polar/cold regions area. A plan of action for the providers of and contributors to the databases will be detailed in order to rationalize the process of data gathering and identification among interested institutions and services, both nationally and internationally.

Indexing overlap and consistency between art and architecture indexes were examined by Angela Giral and Arlene Taylor. Although 71 percent of the sample articles in two secondary sources covering architecture and related infor-

mation were from journals indexed in common, there were numerous differences in article selection, title identification, and access points. If collaboration between the two sources is desired, agreements on such issues as selection criteria, description guidelines, and descriptor terminology will need to be reached.

Vocabularies and Thesauri

Laura Stalker supplied the minutes of the first Conference on Reconciliation of Form and Genre Terminology, partially supported by CLR, which brought together representatives of the major published vocabularies of form and genre terms. Form terms (e.g., diaries, directories, memoranda, questionnaires) designate specific kinds of materials distinguished by physical character, subject, or order of information. Genre terms for textual materials (e.g., biographies, essays, hymns, reviews) designate the style or technique of the intellectual content of textual materials. The conference was held to develop a philosophy and a process for reconciling terms representing form and genre from different controlled vocabularies. In information retrieval systems, distinctions are needed among materials themselves, representations of those materials, and works about the materials. The conference participants reconciled almost thirty terms and established a working procedure for discovering and reconciling term conflicts.

A study to investigate the feasibility of creating a thesaurus for engineering and scientific terms was conducted by Pat Molholt, David Batty, and Cathy Whitehead. They examined the 1967 *Thesaurus of Engineering and Scientific Terms (TEST)* to determine what would be required to use that vocabulary as the basis of a new thesaurus. Their conclusion was that a new thesaurus is warranted, timely, and technically possible, and should be modeled on the *Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)*.

The Music Library Association is also investigating the use of the *Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)* as a subject-specific model vocabulary. Harriette Hemmasi, investigating for Rutgers University, is creating a preliminary music thesaurus utilizing the Anderson Rowley Information Systems (ARIS) software. The overall intent of the project is to increase access to the *Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)* for music materials.

Marcia Bates continued her investigation of expanded access vocabulary for the machine-readable *Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)*.

Preservation

Brittle books are a problem not only for large research and national libraries; they also are found in college libraries. Janet Gertz, Charlotte Brown, Jane Beebe, Daria D'Arienzo, Floyd Merritt, and Lynn Robinson investigated preservation and collection management at liberal arts college libraries. The investigators conducted surveys in three college libraries using a typology methodology defined by Ross Atkinson to determine materials in need of preservation. The results were that significant numbers of brittle low-use volumes were held in the libraries and some of the volumes were materials not widely held, even by research libraries.

Lois Olcott Price, Senior Conservator of the Conservation Center for Art and Historic Artifacts, is preparing a manuscript on the fabrication and preservation of American architectural drawings to 1930. The project's objective is for improved preservation and collection care for architectural drawings and photo reproductions of them through a better understanding of the materials and techniques used in their fabrication. Publication is expected in early 1994.

The United States Agricultural Information Network (USAIN) is proposing a national program to preserve in the original or in an archivally sound format—and to make readily accessible to scholars, researchers, students, and scientists—the most important pre-1950 published literature and the primary unpublished resources that together document the history of the agricultural sciences in the United States. Land-grant institutions, the National Agricultural Library, and other libraries, societies, and archives with important historical collections will participate in the program. The Council provided partial support for an Advisory Panel on Preservation to consider how best to preserve the agricultural science literature. The panel engaged Nancy Gwinn to facilitate the planning process and to draft a national preservation plan.

Collection Development

In her final report to CLR on a study of access versus ownership issues in five libraries, Sheila Intner concluded

that collection development librarians are, for the most part, still deeply committed to perceiving needed materials primarily in terms of printed books and journals, and attempt to the best of their abilities to buy them all. The study population included administrators and collection development staff. Recognizing the limitations of case studies and changing environments, Intner noted that this observation cannot be generalized to the full library community but suggests that these thoughts are echoing in other places. While some study participants may agree that the access function of libraries will grow, others point out that there will continue to be a need for some organization somewhere to collect, organize, and maintain recorded knowledge. Many study participants also do not believe that libraries have either the resources or the will to implement new technologies that have the potential to improve access. Recommendations for the first steps toward an access versus ownership decision-making model are provided.

Use of Technology

The use of technology to provide cost-effective cataloging training was explored by the National Agricultural Library in its development of a hypertext tutorial for the descriptive cataloging of computer files. The experimental tool and project were described in an article by Sarah Thomas. The evaluators were enthusiastic about the potential of such a tool and recommended that other such experiments be undertaken.

Virginia Tiefel visited personnel in thirteen institutions to examine innovative applications of technology to public services in libraries. She developed seventeen criteria to examine the specific applications, and provided descriptions of each of the projects. There is a perception in the profession that libraries require users to know or learn how libraries are organized, so many of these projects are trying to develop systems that are easy for patrons to use. Their goals and objectives include the provision of information to users regardless of their location or the material's format. The libraries have been proactive in the development of the systems in order to ensure their leadership in information technologies and to establish their roles and responsibilities within their organizations.

The Future Catalog

An ongoing research project that has been looking at how to develop an online catalog search system that incorporates aids for clustering and organizing useful retrieval sets is being conducted at the Computer Science Department of Indiana University of Pennsylvania, under the direction of Mary Micco. The system takes advantage of the data included in a bibliographic record, tables of contents, and expert system technology to improve subject access for catalog retrieval. The project has been developed in phases increasing in complexity and scope. With each phase, the feasibility of the concept has been tested and limitations imposed by software and hardware have been examined.

An exploration into the library catalog of the future is being conducted for the Council by Charles Hildreth. He is investigating what form the next generation catalog will take, which projects currently being conducted are potential models for this new catalog, and what characteristics are needed to transform the current static catalog into a dynamic information access and delivery system.

The concept of the digital library or electronic information center is being actively considered by many organizations. In order to provide the necessary background information for developing plans related to the electronic library, the Council has contracted with the University of Michigan's School of Information and Library Studies to conduct an analytical review of the literature on the future library.

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Part III. Project Reports Received

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PROGRAM GUIDELINES AND GRANT APPLICATION PROCEDURES

The Council on Library Resources supports work by individuals and organizations on matters pertinent to libraries and information services, with a primary objective to improve their quality and performance. Since the Council's programs are broad and its program descriptions general, there is continuing refinement and adjustment to the scope of projects funded. Individuals with specific interests and expertise are encouraged to take the initiative and propose for consideration projects within the program areas described in this report: human resources, the economics of information services, infrastructure, and access and processing.

In addition to the general program grants, the Council sponsors the CLR Fellows program and the Cooperative Research program, both of which encourage research projects and the development of research skills by individual professionals. The programs are described in brochures available from CLR.

While CLR, in consultation with its advisors, often initiates and promotes work in its program areas, exploratory correspondence and conversation are always welcome, and all proposals receive careful consideration.

Advice to Applicants

The most efficient means to contact the Council is with a letter or electronic communication. Initial inquiries should state the purpose of the work, indicate methodology, establish the credentials of the responsible individuals, and provide an estimate of the total costs and funding requirements. Enough information should be provided to enable CLR staff to determine whether or not the inquiry falls within the Council's program interests. Letters of application will be briefly acknowledged upon their receipt, but because CLR prefers to operate with a small staff, detailed responses may take more time. If substantive replies are not received within a reasonable period of time, applicants should feel free to make a follow-up inquiry. There are no submission deadlines for general program grants, but the special programs have announced deadlines.

If subsequent exploration seems justified, preparation of a complete proposal will be suggested. Full documentation should include:

1. A concise description of the proposed project.
2. A thorough explanation of the work to be done, including project objectives and background information on the need for the project.
3. Specific methodology to be used.
4. A timetable for the project.
5. A detailed budget linking costs to project components.
6. Plans for evaluation of the project and dissemination of project results.
7. Concise and pertinent curricula vitae of the principal investigators.

Proposals are first reviewed by CLR staff and, when necessary, external technical advisors. All proposals are considered for relevance to current CLR interests and activities; relationship to other, similar work; projected costs in the context of the work described; and importance of anticipated results. The Council also looks for evidence of institutional support, including cost sharing. Grant applications are generally reviewed also by an external proposal review committee, and proposals over \$25,000 need approval from the CLR Board of Directors, which meets twice a year (May and November). However, even proposals that are to be recommended for Board approval cannot in every case be reviewed at the first meeting following their receipt. All inquiries and proposals are reported to the Board, including those declined at the staff and review committee level.

Exclusions

The Council does not provide support for construction, renovation, or other capital improvements. Support is not provided for collection acquisitions, routine operating costs, activities judged to be of limited influence, or work that essentially repeats previous research. CLR does not fund indirect costs. Equipment purchases are also generally not supported, unless integral to a research project.

Contact

Inquiries should be addressed to Julia C. Blixrud, Program Officer, Council on Library Resources, 1400 16th St., N.W., Suite 510, Washington, DC 20036 (202-483-7474 voice, 202-483-6410 fax, clr@cni.org Internet)

ACTIVE PROJECTS
FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS ACTIVE IN FISCAL 1993 (unaudited)

FY 1993

	Unpaid 6/30/92	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/93
<i>American Association of Engineering Societies</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Planning a thesaurus of engineering and scientific terms	9,750	-0-	8,250	1,500
<i>American Library Association</i>				
<i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Standards for ethical conduct for rare book, manuscript, and special collections librarians	1,800	-0-	1,800	-0-
<i>Association of Research Libraries</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
ARL visiting program officer to improve interlibrary loan and document delivery services	-0-	10,700	-0-	10,700
Interlibrary loan cost study	2,000	-0-	-0-	2,000
<i>Marcia Bates</i>				
<i>Van Nuys, Calif.</i>				
Examine the possibility of expanded entry vocabulary for Library of Congress subject headings	6,000	-0-	-0-	6,000
<i>California State University</i>				
<i>Chico, Calif.</i>				
Packet radio Internet extension	1,048	-0-	-0-	1,048
<i>Catholic University of America</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
The information-seeking patterns of faculty members and their use of an online system	-0-	3,513	-0-	3,513
<i>College of William and Mary</i>				
<i>Williamsburg, Va.</i>				
Scholarly humanities communication in the electronic age	-0-	1,725	1,725	-0-
<i>Columbia University</i>				
<i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Recasting scientific information delivery	50,000	(7,694)	-0-	42,306
<i>Conservation Center for Art and Historic Artifacts</i>				
<i>Philadelphia, Pa.</i>				
Research on the preservation and fabrication of American architectural drawings to 1930	1,916	-0-	-0-	1,916

	<i>FY 1993</i>			
	Unpaid 6/30/92	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/93
<i>Earlham College</i> <i>Richmond, Ind.</i> Determining factors leading Earlham College graduates to enter library schools	1,000	(56)	944	-0-
<i>Eckerd College</i> <i>St. Petersburg, Fla.</i> College library director mentor program	16,000	-0-	12,000	4,000
<i>Georgetown University</i> <i>Washington, D.C.</i> Support for the Strategic Visions Steering Committee	5,000	(3,694)	1,306	-0-
<i>Harvard University</i> <i>Cambridge, Mass.</i> Strategic planning process	50,000	-0-	-0-	50,000
<i>Charles R. Hildreth</i> <i>Seattle, Wash.</i> Study of functionality of online catalogs	11,000	-0-	1,000	10,000
<i>Indiana University of Pennsylvania</i> <i>Indiana, Pa.</i> Hypermedia for improved subject access	-0-	6,600	5,500	1,100
Vocabulary control tools for online searching	-0-	54,852 (40,000)	12,000	2,852
<i>International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions</i> <i>The Hague, Netherlands</i> IFLA Fellows program	40,000	-0-	40,000	-0-
<i>Japan Information Access Project</i> <i>Washington, D.C.</i> Symposium on access to, use of, and demand for Japanese information	500	-0-	-0-	500
<i>Johns Hopkins University</i> <i>Baltimore, Md.</i> Information-seeking process among population studies researchers	-0-	4,000	3,500	500
Knowledge management: expanding the scholarly role of research libraries	22,897	-0-	-0-	22,897
<i>Kansas State University</i> <i>Manhattan, Kans.</i> National preservation plan for the historical literature of agriculture	-0-	7,000	6,250	750

		<i>FY 1993</i>		
	Unpaid 6/30/92	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/93
<hr/>				
<i>Library of Congress</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
East European bibliographies and European networks conference	875	-0-	875	-0-
Inaugural meeting of the Cooperative Cataloging Council	-0-	1,961	-0-	1,961
<hr/>				
<i>Long Island University</i>				
<i>Brookville, N.Y.</i>				
Complete study of the effects of integrating information technologies on job classification and compensation systems	3,855	(184)	3,671	-0-
An analytical bibliography on library and information science education	-0-	3,000	-0-	3,000
<hr/>				
<i>National Information Standards Organization</i>				
<i>Bethesda, Md.</i>				
Development of technical standards for the preservation of library materials	10,000	-0-	-0-	10,000
<hr/>				
<i>Queens College</i>				
<i>Flushing, N.Y.</i>				
Seminar series on mapping curricular revision	-0-	6,600	3,500	3,100
<hr/>				
<i>Maxine H. Reneker</i>				
<i>Palo Alto, Calif.</i>				
Information seeking among members of an academic community	500	-0-	500	-0-
<hr/>				
<i>Rice University</i>				
<i>Houston, Tex.</i>				
The Rice humanities electronic studio	-0-	65,000	30,000	35,000
<hr/>				
<i>Rutgers University</i>				
<i>New Brunswick, N.J.</i>				
Study of the costs and beneficial impacts of library functions	-0-	97,612	25,000	72,612
<hr/>				
<i>SKP Associates</i>				
<i>New York, N.Y.</i>				
Evaluation of the Cataloging in Publication program	12,500	-0-	12,500	-0-
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<i>Simmons College</i>				
<i>Boston, Mass.</i>				
Study of the decision-making process for collection development in libraries	859	(466)	393	-0-
<hr/>				
<i>Special Libraries Association</i>				
<i>Washington, D.C.</i>				
Development of continuing education course on total quality management	6,000	-0-	-0-	6,000

		FY 1993		
	Unpaid 6/30/92	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/93
<i>State University of New York</i>				
<i>Buffalo, N.Y.</i>				
Cooperative planning grant	50,000	-0-	50,000	-0-
Study of journal use survey participation	-0-	1,650	1,650	-0-
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Berkeley, Calif.</i>				
History of the Japan Library School as part of U.S. foreign information policy	-0-	2,500	2,500	-0-
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Los Angeles, Calif.</i>				
Elucidation and validation of the knowledge used by reference librarians	1,330	(439)	-0-	891
Technology and structure of research libraries	1,000	-0-	-0-	1,000
<i>University of California</i>				
<i>Riverside, Calif.</i>				
European Short Title Catalogue	16,500	-0-	16,500	-0-
Meeting on standardization of bibliographic form and genre terminology	3,000	-0-	3,000	-0-
<i>University of Colorado</i>				
<i>Boulder, Colo.</i>				
Distributing responsibilities for accessing and indexing polar regions information	15,190	-0-	12,000	3,190
<i>University of Illinois</i>				
<i>Chicago, Ill.</i>				
Users' persistence in scanning postings in an online public access catalog	1,330	-0-	-0-	1,330
<i>University of Illinois</i>				
<i>Urbana, Ill.</i>				
A history of Argentina's National Library under the directorship of Hugo Wast, 1931-1955	500	(1,191)	(691)	-0-
Study of searching strategies on CD-ROM	2,512	(3,552)	(1,040)	-0-
<i>University of Michigan</i>				
<i>Ann Arbor, Mich.</i>				
The library of the future: an analytical report and bibliography	-0-	7,000	6,000	1,000
<i>University of North Carolina</i>				
<i>Chapel Hill, N.C.</i>				
Cooperative information resources development	50,000	(10,000)	40,000	-0-

		FY 1993		
	Unpaid 6/30/92	Grants and Contracts (Adjustments)	Payments (Refunds)	Unpaid 6/30/93
<hr/>				
<i>University of Pittsburgh</i> <i>Pittsburgh, Pa.</i>				
Examination of the effects of integrating information technologies on job classification and compensation systems	1,560	-0-	1,560	-0-
<hr/>				
<i>University of South Carolina</i> <i>Columbia, S.C.</i>				
Study of the knowledge and skills required for health information professionals	1,616	-0-	1,616	-0-
<hr/>				
<i>Urban Libraries Council</i> <i>Evanston, Ill.</i>				
Seminar on successful public library financial practices	500	(60)	440	-0-
<hr/>				
<i>Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University</i> <i>Blacksburg, Va.</i>				
Blacksburg electronic village project	-0-	9,665	-0-	9,665
<hr/>				
<i>Yale University</i> <i>New Haven, Conn.</i>				
Instant mathematics preprint project	1,500	(1,500)	-0-	-0-
<hr/>				
Current year adjustments; other refunds and adjustments from prior year's grants and contracts	-0-	(297)	(297)	-0-
<hr/>				
Totals	\$400,038	\$283,378 (69,133)	\$305,980 (2,028)	\$310,331

INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

TO THE BOARD OF DIRECTORS
COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.
Washington, D.C.

We have audited the balance sheet of COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC. (the "Council") as of June 30, 1993, and the related statements of revenue, expenses and changes in fund balance, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit. The financial statements of the Council as of June 30, 1992, were audited by other auditors whose report dated August 20, 1992, expressed an unqualified opinion on those statements and are included for comparative purposes only.

We conducted our audit in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the 1993 financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC. as of June 30, 1993, and the results of its operations and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The accompanying supplementary information is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Vienna, Virginia
August 20, 1993

BALANCE SHEET

JUNE 30, 1993

(With Comparative Totals For 1992)

	<u>1993</u>	Totals <u>1992</u>
<i>ASSETS</i>		
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 208,056	\$ 377,267
Investments	1,782,386	2,438,355
Grants receivable:		
Unrestricted	300,000	600,000
Restricted	213,000	200,000
Other assets	<u>16,984</u>	<u>8,980</u>
	<u>\$ 2,520,426</u>	<u>\$ 3,624,602</u>
 <i>LIABILITIES AND FUND BALANCE</i>		
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 17,567	\$ 13,536
Grants and contracts payable:		
Unrestricted	65,396	116,640
Restricted	244,935	283,398
Deferred revenue:		
Unrestricted	600,000	900,000
Restricted (Note C)	<u>142,131</u>	<u>337,852</u>
Total liabilities	1,070,029	1,651,426
 <i>FUND BALANCE:</i>		
Designated by Board of Directors (Note B)	939	47,589
Undesignated	<u>1,449,458</u>	<u>1,925,587</u>
Total fund balance	<u>1,450,397</u>	<u>1,973,176</u>
	<u>\$ 2,520,426</u>	<u>\$ 3,624,602</u>

SEE NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

STATEMENT OF REVENUE, EXPENSES AND CHANGES IN FUND BALANCE

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1993
(With Comparative Totals For 1992)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total 1993</u>	<u>Totals 1992</u>
REVENUE:				
Grants and contracts	\$ 300,000	\$208,721	\$ 508,721	\$ 501,343
Interest	<u>118,605</u>	<u>2,047</u>	<u>120,652</u>	<u>216,304</u>
Total revenue	418,605	210,768	629,373	717,647
EXPENSES:				
Program:				
Research	—	27,864	27,864	155,458
Human resources	156,840	41,371	198,211	163,824
Access and processing	159,351	(13)	159,338	154,019
Economics	83,124	141,546	224,670	119,642
Infrastructure	<u>242,383</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>242,383</u>	<u>149,405</u>
Total program expenses	641,698	210,768	852,466	742,348
Administration	<u>299,686</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>299,686</u>	<u>403,355</u>
Total expenses	<u>941,384</u>	<u>210,768</u>	<u>1,152,152</u>	<u>1,145,703</u>
EXCESS (DEFICIENCY) OF REVENUE OVER EXPENSES	(522,779)	—	(522,779)	(428,056)
FUND BALANCE, BEGINNING OF YEAR	<u>1,973,176</u>	<u>—</u>	<u>1,973,176</u>	<u>2,401,232</u>
FUND BALANCE, END OF YEAR	<u>\$1,450,397</u>	<u>\$ —</u>	<u>\$1,450,397</u>	<u>\$1,973,176</u>

SEE NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1993

(With Comparative Totals For 1992)

	<u>1993</u>	Totals <u>1992</u>
CASH FLOWS FROM OPERATING ACTIVITIES:		
Excess (deficiency) of revenue over expenses	\$ (522,779)	\$ (428,056)
Adjustments to reconcile deficiency of revenue over expenses to net cash used in operating activities:		
Amortization of investment (discounts) premiums	(5,464)	415
(Increase) decrease in grants receivable	287,000	(800,000)
Decrease in other assets	12,946	42,108
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	4,031	(3,110)
Decrease in grants and contracts payable	(89,707)	(98,513)
(Decrease) increase in deferred revenue	<u>(495,721)</u>	<u>693,757</u>
Total adjustments	<u>(286,915)</u>	<u>(165,343)</u>
Net cash used in operating activities	<u>(809,694)</u>	<u>(593,399)</u>
CASH FLOWS FROM INVESTING ACTIVITIES:		
Purchase of investments	(1,459,517)	(1,003,994)
Sale of investments	<u>2,100,000</u>	<u>1,500,000</u>
Net cash provided by investing activities	<u>640,483</u>	<u>496,006</u>
NET DECREASE IN CASH AND CASH EQUIVALENTS	(169,211)	(97,393)
CASH AND CASH EQUIVALENTS, BEGINNING OF YEAR	<u>377,267</u>	<u>474,660</u>
CASH AND CASH EQUIVALENTS, END OF YEAR	<u>\$208,056</u>	<u>\$377,267</u>

SEE NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

JUNE 30, 1993

A. ORGANIZATION

Council on Library Resources, Inc. (the "Council") is a nonprofit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1956 for the purpose of promoting library research.

The Council's operations are financed through unrestricted general support grants and through several restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work through directly administered projects as well as grants to and contracts with other organizations or individuals.

B. SUMMARY OF SIGNIFICANT ACCOUNTING POLICIES

The significant accounting policies followed in the preparation of the financial statements are described below:

Basis of accounting

The financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue

Grants to the Council are recorded as grants receivable and as deferred grant revenues when awarded. Revenues of restricted grant funds are recognized only to the extent of expenditures that satisfy the restricted purposes of these grants.

Unrestricted grant revenue is recognized as income in accordance with the allocated annual payments specified by the grantors.

Grants and contracts payable

Grants and contracts made by the Council are recorded as grants and contracts payable and as an expense at the time recipients are awarded the grants. Current period expenses are reduced for grant or contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Cash and cash equivalents, and investments

Cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market mutual fund. Cash equivalents represent investments with original maturities of 90 days or less. Investments which consist of treasury notes and treasury bills are recorded at amortized cost which approximates market. Interest which is not restricted by the related grants is recognized as unrestricted revenue.

Functional allocation of expenses

Costs of providing the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs identified as support services costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a systematic basis. These costs primarily include salary, benefits, rent and other expenses.

Board designated funds

In prior years, the Board of Directors had designated a portion of the fund balance for various short-term projects. During 1993, amounts totalling \$9,000 were transferred to the undesignated fund balance, representing a reduction in costs of the Council's Academic Library Management Intern Program.

Reclassification

Certain amounts have been reclassified in the accompanying 1992 financial statements to conform to the 1993 presentation. This primarily relates to combining the accrued interest with the investments.

C. CHANGES IN RESTRICTED DEFERRED REVENUE

Balance, beginning of year	\$ 337,852
Additions:	
Contract	13,000
Deductions, funds expended or refunded during the year:	
Grants	<u>(208,721)</u>
Balance, end of year	<u>\$ 142,131</u>

D. INCOME TAXES

The Council, a private operating foundation, is exempt from federal income tax under § 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

E. RETIREMENT PLAN

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council's contributions. The Council's contribution was \$52,182 in fiscal year 1993.

F. CONCENTRATIONS OF CREDIT RISK

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents, investments and grants receivable.

At June 30, 1993, approximately \$191,400 in cash equivalents was being held by a third party in a money market mutual fund that invests solely in United States government securities. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation.

Substantially all grants receivable are with large foundations. It is not the Council's policy to require collateral for these receivables. Generally, the Council has not incurred any losses in relation to these receivables.

STATEMENT OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 1993
 (With Comparative Totals For 1992)

	<u>Research</u>	<u>Human Resources</u>	<u>Access and Processing</u>
UNRESTRICTED:			
Grants and contracts	\$ —	\$ 12,100	\$ 76,877
Refunds and over appropriations	—	(5,221)	(40,466)
Staff and travel	—	40,910	41,954
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	—	44,764	16,699
Board expenses	—	—	—
Support services, including office expenses	<u>—</u>	<u>64,287</u>	<u>64,287</u>
	<u>—</u>	<u>156,840</u>	<u>159,351</u>
RESTRICTED:			
Grants and contracts	32,250	—	—
Refunds and over appropriations	(23,373)	—	(13)
Staff and travel	2,000	571	—
Advisory committees, consultants and interns	1,424	40,795	—
Support services, including office expenses	<u>15,563</u>	<u>5</u>	<u>—</u>
	<u>27,864</u>	<u>41,371</u>	<u>(13)</u>
	<u>\$ 27,864</u>	<u>\$ 198,211</u>	<u>\$ 159,338</u>

SEE NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

<u>Economics</u>	<u>Infrastructure</u>	<u>Total Program Expenses</u>	<u>Administrative</u>	<u>Total 1993</u>	<u>Totals 1992</u>
\$ —	\$ 53,839	\$142,816	\$ —	\$ 142,816	\$ 127,037
—	—	(45,687)	—	(45,687)	(2,685)
11,058	45,337	139,259	166,070	305,329	378,016
7,779	77,779	147,021	13,526	160,547	111,814
—	—	—	28,456	28,456	32,196
<u>64,287</u>	<u>65,428</u>	<u>258,289</u>	<u>91,634</u>	<u>349,923</u>	<u>294,947</u>
<u>83,124</u>	<u>242,383</u>	<u>641,698</u>	<u>299,686</u>	<u>941,384</u>	<u>941,325</u>
108,312	—	140,562	—	140,562	149,242
(60)	—	(23,446)	—	(23,446)	(70,586)
30,306	—	32,877	—	32,877	9,414
2,988	—	45,207	—	45,207	40,885
—	—	<u>15,568</u>	—	<u>15,568</u>	<u>75,423</u>
<u>141,546</u>	—	<u>210,768</u>	—	<u>210,768</u>	<u>204,378</u>
<u>\$224,670</u>	<u>\$242,383</u>	<u>\$852,466</u>	<u>\$299,686</u>	<u>\$1,152,152</u>	<u>\$1,145,703</u>

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